

α -PARACOMPACT SUBSETS AND WELL-SITUATED SUBSETS

by

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Abstract. We study some properties of α -paracompact subsets, defined by C.E.Aull. Moreover we consider R.Telgársky's well-situated subsets, in connection with Tamano's problem. The last section of the paper is the solution to a problem of Telgársky.

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α -paracompact subset	perfect mapping	class II
well-situated subset	paracompact space	embedding

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Introduction

In Section 1 we study α -paracompact subsets, defined by C.E. Aull. Here we obtain some covering properties of α -paracompact subsets which are similar to properties of paracompact spaces. In particular, we characterize α -paracompact subsets in regular spaces. Moreover we study the behaviour of α -paracompact subsets under perfect mappings.

In Section 2 we consider R. Telgársky's well-situated subsets. The properties of α -paracompact subsets of Section 1 yield properties of well-situated subsets. Well-situated subsets are related to Tamano's problem (i.e.: to give an intrinsic description of those T_2 spaces X such that $X \times Y$ is paracompact for each paracompact T_2 space Y) which remains open.

In Section 3 we solve a problem of Telgársky. We establish that: In the realm of T_2 spaces, the class Π^* is perfect.

1. α -Paracompact subsets

C.E. Aull defined in [1] the notion of an α -paracompact subset. A subset E of a topological space X is said to be α -paracompact in X if every covering of E by open subsets of X has a refinement by open subsets of X , locally finite in X , which covers E . We continue in this paper the study about α -paracompact subsets. We omit the proofs in this section.

1.1. Proposition: Let X be a topological space. Then:

1) If E is an α -paracompact subset in X and F is a subset of E which is closed in X , then F is α -paracompact in X .

2) If $\{E_j\}_{j \in J}$ is a set of subsets of X , locally finite in X and such that E_j is α -paracompact in X for every $j \in J$ and there exists a locally finite family of open subsets $\{U_j\}_{j \in J}$ of X such that $E_j \subset U_j$ for every $j \in J$, then $\bigcup_{j \in J} E_j$ is α -paracompact in X .

In particular, all finite union of α -paracompact subsets is α -paracompact.

1.2. Remark. In the last proposition, in 2) the hypothesis "locally finite family $\{U_j\}_{j \in J}$ " cannot be replaced by the hypothesis "locally finite set $\{U_j\}_{j \in J}$ " (a set is a family formed by members pairwise different). In fact, in the Niemytski plane, $X = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 / y \geq 0\}$ (in which if $y_0 > 0$, let neighbourhoods of (x_0, y_0) be the usual neighbourhoods of the plane relativized with respect to X , if $y_0 = 0$ let neighbourhoods of $(x_0, 0)$ consist of open circles with center (x_0, y) and radius y with the point $(x_0, 0)$ for each $y > 0$). $\{E_q\}_{q \in \mathbb{Q}}$ where $E_q = \{(q, 0)\}$ is a locally finite set of α -paracompact subsets of X such that $\bigcup_{q \in \mathbb{Q}} E_q$ is not α -paracompact ([1] p. 50), and $\{U_q\}_{q \in \mathbb{Q}}$ where $U_q = X$ for each $q \in \mathbb{Q}$, this is a locally finite set such that $E_q \subset U_q$ for each $q \in \mathbb{Q}$.

1.3. Theorem. Let X be a regular space and E a subset of X . The following conditions are equivalent:

- a) E is an α -paracompact subset in X .
- b) 1) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement $\mathcal{V}$ by open subsets of X , σ -locally finite in X , which covers E , and 2) Every open subset U of X such that $E \subset U$ has an open subset V such that $E \subset V \subset \bar{V} \subset U$.
- c) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement $\mathcal{A} = \{A_s\}_{s \in S}$ by arbitrary sets of X , locally finite in X ,

such that $E \subset \overline{\bigcup_{s \in S} A_s}$.

d) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement $\mathcal{F} = \{F_j\}_{j \in J}$ by closed subsets of X , locally finite in X ,

such that $E \subset \overline{\bigcup_{j \in J} F_j}$.

Remark. From 1.3 follows Corollary 3 and Theorem 4 of [1].

1.4. Proposition. Let X be a regular space and E an α -paracompact subset in X . Then:

1) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement by open subsets of X , barycentric in X , which covers E .

2) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a star refinement by open subsets of X which covers E .

1.5. Proposition. Let X be a regular space and E an α -paracompact subset in X . Then for every family $\{F_s\}_{s \in S}$ of subsets of E , locally finite (discrete) in X , there is a family $\{U_s\}_{s \in S}$ of open subsets of X , locally finite (discrete) in X such that $F_s \subset U_s$ for every $s \in S$.

We pass now to study the behaviour of the α -paracompact subsets under perfect mappings.

1.6. Proposition. Let X and X' be topological spaces and $f: X \rightarrow X'$ a perfect mapping. If E' is an α -paracompact subset in X' then $f^{-1}(E')$ is an α -paracompact subset in X .

1.7. Remark. From last Proposition it follows that: if X and Y are topological spaces, E is an α -paracompact subset in X and Y is compact, then $E \times Y$ is an α -paracompact subset in $X \times Y$.

But, if X and Y are topological spaces, E is an α -paracompact subset in X and F is an α -paracompact subset in Y , $E \times F$ is not necessarily an α -paracompact subset in $X \times Y$. In fact: $\mathbb{Q}$ is an α -paracompact subset in the Michael line $\mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{Q}}$ (see [2] p. 384), $\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}$ is an α -paracompact subset in $\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}$, but $\mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ is not an α -paracompact subset in $\mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{Q}} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ (because the sets $\mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ and $C = \{(x, x) / x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}\}$ are disjoint closed sets which are not strongly separated, it follows from Theorem 5 in [1] that $\mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ is not an α -paracompact subset).

1.8. Proposition. Let X and X' be topological spaces, where X is regular, f a perfect mapping from X onto X' and E' a subset of X' . If $f^{-1}(E')$ is an α -paracompact subset in X then E' is an α -paracompact subset in X' .

1.9. Remark. In the last Proposition the hypothesis "f mapping onto" cannot be omitted. In fact: let $\mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{Q}}$ be the Michael line, the mapping $i: \mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}) \hookrightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{Q}} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ is a perfect mapping but is not onto, $\mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ is an α -paracompact subset in $\mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ with the usual topology and $\mathbb{Q} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ is not an α -paracompact subset in $\mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{Q}} \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ (see 1.7).

1.10. Proposition. Let X and X' be topological spaces and f a perfect and open mapping from X onto X' ; if E is an α -paracompact subset in X then $f(E)$ is an α -paracompact subset in X' .

1.11. Remark. Let X and X' be topological spaces and f a perfect mapping from X onto X' ; if E is an α -paracompact subset in X , $f(E)$ is not necessarily α -paracompact in X' . In fact: let $\mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{Q}}$ be the Michael line,

$j_1: Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) \hookrightarrow Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) + \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$ and
 $j_2: \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) \hookrightarrow Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) + \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$, the mapping onto
 $f: Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) + \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$ such that
 $f(j_1(x, y)) = (x, y)$ if $(x, y) \in Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$
 $f(j_2(x, y)) = (x, y)$ if $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$
 is a perfect mapping, $f(j_1(Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q))) = Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$,
 $j_1(Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q))$ is an α -paracompact subset in $Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q) + \mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$
 and $Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$ is not an α -paracompact subset in $\mathbb{R}_Q \times (\mathbb{R} \setminus Q)$ (1.7)

2. Well-situated subsets.

The concept of a well-situated subset was introduced by R. Telgársky in [4]. Using the notion of an α -paracompact subset, H.W. Martin phrase the definition of a well-situated subset of a space X as follows: a subset E of a space X is said to be well-situated in X if for every paracompact T_2 space Y , $E \times Y$ is an α -paracompact subset in $X \times Y$ ([5]).

If E is a well-situated subset of a space X , then E is an α -paracompact subset in X , but Q is α -paracompact in $\mathbb{R}_Q$, the Michael line, and Q is not a well-situated subset in $\mathbb{R}_Q$ (1.7).

From Section 1 it follows easily analogous results for well-situated subsets. In particular:

2.1. Theorem. Let X be a regular space and E a subset of X . The following conditions are equivalent:

- a) E is a well-situated subset in X .
- b) For every paracompact T_2 space Y : 1) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of $E \times Y$ by open subsets of $X \times Y$ has a refinement $\mathcal{V}$ by open subsets of $X \times Y$, σ -locally finite in $X \times Y$, which covers $E \times Y$, and 2) Every open subset U of $X \times Y$ such that $E \times Y \subset U$ has an open subset

V such that $E \times Y \subset V \subset \bar{V} \subset U$.

c) For every paracompact T_2 space Y , every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of $E \times Y$ by open subsets of $X \times Y$ has a refinement $\mathcal{A} = \{A_s\}_{s \in S}$ by arbitrary sets of $X \times Y$, locally finite in $X \times Y$, such that

$$E \times Y \subset \bigcup_{s \in S} A_s.$$

d) For every paracompact T_2 space Y , every covering of $E \times Y$ by open subsets of $X \times Y$ has a refinement $\mathcal{F} = \{F_j\}_{j \in J}$ by closed subsets of $X \times Y$, locally finite in $X \times Y$, such that $E \times Y \subset \bigcup_{j \in J} F_j$.

2.2. Proposition. Let X and X' be topological spaces and $f: X \rightarrow X'$ a perfect mapping. If E' is a well-situated subset in X' then $f^{-1}(E')$ is a well-situated subset in X .

2.3. Proposition. Let X and X' be topological spaces, where X is regular, f a perfect mapping from X onto X' and E' a subset of X' . If $f^{-1}(E')$ is a well-situated subset in X then E' is a well-situated subset in X' .

2.4. Proposition. Let X and X' be topological spaces and f a perfect and open mapping from X onto X' ; if E is a well-situated subset in X then $f(E)$ is a well-situated subset in X' .

3. The class Π^*

In [4] R. Telgársky denoted by Π^* the class of all paracompact T_2 spaces which are well-situated in every paracompact T_2 space in which are embedded as closed subsets.

R. Telgársky showed which Π^* is a very wide class contained in the class Π of all T_2 spaces X such that $X \times Y$ is paracom-

compact for each paracompact T_2 space Y , and he raised the following questions:

1. In the class Π^* perfect? ([4], Problem 2.1)
2. Does the class of all paracompact $\underline{C}$ -scattered spaces coincide with the class Π^* ? ([4], Problem 2.3).

In the present paper, we shall give an affirmative answer to question 1.

3.1. Proposition. Let E and E' be topological spaces where E is T_2 , and f a perfect mapping from E onto E' . If $E' \in \Pi^*$ then $E \in \Pi^*$.

Proof. Let X a paracompact T_2 space such that E is embedded in X as a closed subset. Let $j_1: X \rightarrow X+E'$, $j_2: E' \rightarrow X+E'$ be the embeddings of the subspaces X and E' in the sum $X+E'$, let

$X \bigcup_f E'$ be the adjunction space determined by X , E' and f and

let $q: X+E' \rightarrow X \bigcup_f E'$ be the natural quotient mapping. As the mapping f is closed, q is a continuous and closed mapping; since $X+E'$ is paracompact and T_2 , $X \bigcup_f E'$ is paracompact (it follows from the Michael Theorem) and T_2 .

$q \circ j_2: E' \rightarrow X \bigcup_f E'$ is a homeomorphic embedding and $(q \circ j_2)(E')$ is closed in $X \bigcup_f E'$. Since $E' \in \Pi^*$ and $X \bigcup_f E'$ is paracompact and T_2 , $(q \circ j_2)(E')$ is a well-situated subset in $X \bigcup_f E'$.

Let $\hat{f} = q \circ j_1: X \rightarrow X \bigcup_f E'$. Clearly $\hat{f}$ is a perfect mapping.

Since $(q \circ j_2)(E')$ is a well-situated subset in $X \cup_f E'$, from 2.2. it follows that $\hat{f}^{-1}((q \circ j_2)(E'))$ is a well-situated subset in X . But $\hat{f}^{-1}((q \circ j_2)(E')) = j_1^{-1}(q^{-1}(q(j_2(E')))) = E$. Thus E is a well-situated subset in X . Hence $E \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$.

3.2. Proposition. Let E and E' be topological spaces and f a perfect mapping from E onto E' . If $E \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$ then $E' \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$.

Proof. Since f is continuous, $G_f = \{(x, f(x)) \in E \times E' / x \in E\}$ is homeomorphic to E , then $G_f \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$.

Since E is $T_{3\frac{1}{2}}$ and f is a perfect mapping from E onto E' , G_f is a closed subset of $\beta E \times E'$ (See [5], proof of Theorem 3.10). Let X' a paracompact T_2 space such that E' is embedded in X' as a closed subset, then G_f is a closed subset of $\beta E \times X'$ which is paracompact and T_2 , thus G_f is a well-situated subset in $\beta E \times X'$.

The projection $p_2: \beta E \times X' \rightarrow X'$ is perfect and open, and $p_2(G_f) = E'$. From 2.4 it follows that E' is a well-situated subset in X' .

3.3. Theorem. In the realm of T_2 spaces, the class $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$ is perfect (i.e., if E and E' are topological spaces where E is T_2 and f is a perfect mapping from E onto E' then $E \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$ if and only if $E' \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^*$).

Proof. It follows from 3.1 and 3.2.

Added. The author learned, after writing this paper, that J.D. Wine [in: Locally paracompact spaces, Glasnik Mat., 10 (30) (1975),

351-357] has obtained Proposition 1.1.2), and that I. Kovačević [in: Subsets and paracompactness, Zbornik Radova PMF Univ. u Novom Sadu, ser. Mat. 14 (1984), 79-87] has obtained also the implication $a) \Rightarrow b)$ of the Theorem 1.3.

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